

Stepping up data literacy and research impact in the Humanities through data publishing

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Summary. This poster presents work related to promoting peer-reviewed data papers across the humanities, focusing on experiences of the Journal of Open Humanities Data (JOHD). It provides information on the publication and review process, and points out opportunities to engage with the ongoing reform of research assessment and teaching and training efforts.

The open research movement and initiatives like the FAIR principles have been critical in establishing the importance of data in research (Wilkinson et al., 2016). Attention to openly available data in Humanities and Social Sciences (HSS) research has gradually grown which can be attributed to the increased availability of digital collections, the development of new data-intensive methods, increasingly solid infrastructures, funder requirements and the involvement of research libraries in data curation. Additional efforts are needed to embed research data management skills into educational programmes (Engelhardt et al. 2022).

Focusing on the experience of the Journal of Open Humanities Data (JOHD), this poster examines current work to promote peer-reviewed data papers across the humanities. JOHD publishes two kinds of fully peer-reviewed data papers: short papers containing a concise and structured description of a humanities dataset and full-length papers discussing methods, challenges, and limitations in the creation, collection, management, access, processing, or analysis of humanities research data.

Since its launch in 2015, JOHD has grown significantly and has become an important player in raising awareness of data sharing and open data publishing in the humanities. One such example is the social media campaign #showmeyourdata where JOHD authors were invited to post

a tweet showcasing an image of their datasets. Moreover, McGillivray et al. (2022) analyzed the effect that publishing data papers has on the citations of associated research articles and views of associated datasets.

The poster will also look at the place of humanities data publishing in the broader research publication ecosystem. Data publishing can contribute significantly to the development of a framework for evaluating data creation, sharing, and reuse in the context of the recently started reform of research assessment (CoARA, 2022) which encourages institutions to design and implement new assessment criteria that consider diverse research outputs beyond traditional journal publications – data papers should be included as they are well placed to demonstrate efforts of robustness and transparency of research.

Bibliography

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